

Personifying instructional leadership practices in the Centers of Excellence – Colleges of Nursing in the Philippines: A multi-case study design

Mary Nellie T. Roa*

Nursing Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding Author: mnroa@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

The administration of curriculum and instruction by an institution's head is commonly described in instructional leadership. In recent times, the scope of instructional leadership has widened to include more dispersed strategies that emphasize shared and distributed empowerment among school staff, such as distributed leadership, shared leadership, and transformational leadership. Personifying the core values of the university is an instructional leadership disposition that captures the instructional leadership dimensions espoused by Hallinger et al. (2014) which are the following: (a) defining the school's mission (b) managing the instructional program and (c) promoting a positive school learning climate. The integrated characters espoused by the nursing leaders are the following: (a) driving the university vision within the Nursing curriculum (b) transformative leadership (c) sense of purpose and direction (d) symbolic leadership (e) leading the instructional program (f) leading as servant, catalyst and coach and (g) organizational leadership. Instructional leadership dimensions should be rooted in the systems and processes of the nursing faculty. Leaders should be drivers of the vision, mission and core values of the university. In the same manner, managing instructional programs must be established and fostering a caring and productive learning environment must be deeply felt and imbued. Nursing leaders must symbolize the instructional leadership dimensions beyond supervisory functions. The role of nursing leaders on the instructional leadership dimensions must evolve to a level that will be transcendent to personify the core beliefs of the university.

Keywords: *Personifying, instructional leadership, center of excellence, college of nursing.*

To cite this article:

Roa, M. N. T. (2021). Personifying instructional leadership practices in the Centers of Excellence – Colleges of Nursing in the Philippines: A multi-case study design. *Faculty Research Journal – Nursing*, 7, 9-18.

Introduction

The quantum leap in the educational landscape in the 21st century has emphasized the transformative role of educational institutions to provide quality, purposeful, and well-planned instruction, which likely results in an escalation of the level of status of the academic programs in an institution of higher learning. As it has been claimed and true to its impact on educational supervision and leadership, a system of education can only be as good as its teachers (Barber & Mourshed, 2007). Furthermore, the start of the 21st century has seen a major focus in the field of education on the ongoing need for increased responsibility to improve student achievement. Local schools concentrate on carrying out the requirements as best they can, as mandated by national and state expectations, which call for schools to guarantee that all pupils learn the curriculum objectives. Because teachers are the main front-line educators for their pupils, guiding instructional activities in a school has consequently become a primary duty for them (Abreha, 2014; Stronge et al., 2011).

Up until this point, teachers in the United States must concentrate on teaching and learning to a higher degree, particularly in terms of evident student achievement, in order to fulfill the challenges connected with national and state expectations. As a result, modern educators focus on creating a vision for their institutions, delegating leadership responsibilities among themselves, and persuading institutions to function as learning communities. Gathering and evaluating data to identify requirements and keeping an eye on curriculum and instruction to see if the needs are being met are necessary steps towards completing these crucial school improvement initiatives (Liu et al., 2018).

The high board exam results are one of the performance metrics in the Philippines. To achieve this, educational institutions uphold and enforce internal standards that are derived from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). These standards explain excellent teaching techniques that stakeholders should consider adopting to ensure comprehensive academic operations. The Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), another regulatory organization that conducts graduate licensure exams, evaluates the effectiveness of educational programs like the Bachelor of Science in Nursing by administering the Nursing Licensure Examination (NLE). Additionally, the clinical instructors of the Philippines mostly apply the traditional type of leaders who do not have sufficient hands-on experience when it comes to teacher evaluation, budgeting, scheduling, and facility maintenance with a deep involvement towards the delivery of quality teaching and learning that will achieve a higher passing percentage in the Nursing Licensure Examination.

Research on effective schools that support high achievement levels suggests that they may have successfully connected leadership and academic accomplishment with limited resources. Thus, research has identified the two facets of a leader's job, which are overseeing the school as an institution and making significant contributions to it. Teachers at successful schools may have quite different skills; some may be better managers, while others may be more personally powerful leaders. They may have put in less planning, but their intuition and experience allow them to handle problems more skillfully when they emerge. Additionally, they frequently describe their roles differently depending on the context in which they work. There are those who solve problems, those who plan strategically, and those who work as ambassadors. The importance of schools and leadership in bringing about instructional change has been thoroughly investigated, but the attitudes and values that form the basis of instructional leadership have received less attention (Burch et al., 2020).

Given the foregoing premises, the researcher has taken the challenge to explore the leadership style, particularly the instructional leadership of the college deans and clinical coordinators of Centers of Excellence in Colleges of Nursing schools (COE-CONs) in the Philippines by looking into the different dimensions of their instructional leadership, which are mandated and recognized as the hallmark for having exemplarily demonstrated the highest degree or level of standard along with the areas of instruction, research and extension, and administration, among others (Batac, 2007).

As it comes to pass, the researcher believes that the different roles must be extended beyond the work scope of the teacher and must play a critical role in the comprehensive model of instructional leadership (Hallinger, 2003, 2005, 2007, 2010, 2015; Hallinger & Murphy, 1986). The three primary elements of the instructional leadership structure that this dominant model supports are establishing the goal of the school, managing the curriculum, and creating a nurturing learning environment.

In fact, the project has given the College of Nursing's deans and clinical coordinators the opportunity to evaluate how well they have taught students using the three facets of instructional leadership. Through the instructors' adequate leadership abilities, the pursuit of this ultimate objective will probably lead the students to attain outstanding educational outcomes in the board examination. It has also allowed the level coordinators or the team leaders to transform their respective units by sending the teachers to professional enhancement and skills upgrading programs, as well as develop more interventional and developmental programs. Hence, the goal of creating a framework based on the COE-CONs is to enhance the clinical instructors' and nursing administrators' instructional leadership, as there are always opportunities to improve further existing academic practices in the purview of national and global lenses in the years ahead.

Methodology

The study employed a qualitative design, primarily a multi-case study. The qualitative research design is an approach used extensively to understand human behaviors, opinions, perceptions, feelings, and motivations of individuals within the phenomenon of interest (Yin, 2015). The study was conducted at the Centers of Excellence Nursing Schools in the Philippines. A department within a higher education institution that consistently exhibits exceptional performance in the domains of instruction, research and publication, extension and linkages, and institutional credentials is referred to as a Center of Excellence (COE) (Puno, 2006). The criteria for the identification of a center of excellence are based on instructional quality, research and publication, extension and linkages, and institutional qualifications. Based on these selection criteria, among the colleges of nursing in the Philippines, there are only six given such recognition. Among the six COEs-CON, four universities were selected, located across regions of the Philippines.

Results

Educational institutions for the health professions have evolved from non-pedagogical preparation to a more efficient and effective formulation of curricula and equipping the teacher with appropriate pedagogical knowledge and skills. The expectations of society have become a major motivation for the development and training of health professionals (Sana, 2010).

Nursing schools in the Philippines are mandated to provide the best education for students so they can, in the end, serve society with the highest standards of competence and utmost care. The transition from “competency-based to outcomes-based education” is implemented by these policies, standards, and guidelines in accordance with the implementation of CHED Memorandum Order No. 46 s. 2012 (Licuanan, 2012). In addition to providing “*ample space for HEIs offering Bachelor of Science in Nursing programs to innovate in the curriculum in line with the assessment of how best to achieve learning outcomes in their particular contexts and their respective missions,*” this PSG outlines the core competencies expected of BS Nursing graduates regardless of the type of HEIs they graduate from (Licuanan, 2017). According to Section 4 of CMO 15 s. 2017: Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are free to create curricula that best suit their own goals and context as long as they can show how, even though a different path, the curriculum delivery helps students achieve the program outcomes and leads to the minimum necessary professional nursing outcomes.

The goal of the BSN program is to produce professional nurses who can work in community settings and healthcare facilities at entry level. In addition to providing safe, compassionate, high-quality, and comprehensive care to individuals of any age, gender, or health status, professional nurses can also work independently or in unison with other healthcare practitioners to serve the community, healthy or at-risk families, and population groups. They can also help with end-of-life care, preventing disease, restoring health, and reducing pain.

The Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order (CMO) 15 series of 2017 is the year of Philippine policies, standards, and guidelines for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program. The CMO explicitly articulates the nursing curriculum with the promulgated program outcomes, BSN-level outcomes, performance indicators, curriculum, and sample curriculum map. All Philippine nursing schools uphold these statutory standards, and among the 450 schools, six emerged as centers of excellence in nursing (Licuanan, 2017).

It is worthwhile to recognize nursing schools that have excelled and rose among others; as a result, they have been recognized by the Commission on Higher Education as Centers of Excellence. The Manual of Regulations for Higher Education (MORPHE) Article X states that accredited higher education institutions are named Centers of Excellence by the Commission in accordance with the 1991 Education Commission Report, which advocated for supporting the growth of world-class scholarship in the many disciplines in the Philippines (CHED, 2009).

The following are the duties and minimum standards for Centers of Excellence: they must maintain and improve their research capabilities and expand professional and graduate programs in the field; they must act as leaders and role models in the local, regional, and national community through disseminating their best practices and initiating novel approaches; they must offer technical support to organizations and agencies within their service area; and they must carry out other projects and activities required to provide high-quality education in the particular discipline by exchanging developmental programs.

CHED Memorandum Order No. 17 Series of 2006 is the implementing guidelines for the identification, support, and development of Centers of Excellence for health-related education programs. It defines Centers of Excellence as a unit within any higher education institution with the following characteristics: must be accredited Level III program under the Federation of Accrediting Agencies of the Philippines (FAAP); must have obtained an average of at least 90% percentage passing for the last five years in the licensure examination given by their respective professional regulatory board by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC); must have an updated alumni profile and active alumni programs; evidence of innovations or improvements in instruction, participation in research, and community extension are required; academic and research outputs must be acknowledged on a national and worldwide scale, and there must be significant connections between the local and global communities (Pacis et al., 2020).

With all these established and performed by the centers of excellence in nursing, it can be gleaned that the leadership of the dean has a significant effect on how one touches the hearts and minds of those who served in the nursing program, most especially the students. More importantly, instructional leadership plays a significant role, as it is commonly defined as the management of curriculum and instruction by an institution's head. This phrase originated from studies conducted during the 1980s active school movement, which showed that the role of the head of school plays an important part in the success of a school. Recently, the field of instructional leadership has evolved to include a wider range of strategies, including shared, distributed, and transformational leadership, which emphasizes the empowerment of school staff members in both shared and distributed ways.

The school head, as an instructional leader, must concentrate on his function in the cultivation and dissemination of knowledge, abilities, and characteristics throughout the range of school organizational structures. The head of the school is not the only person whose leadership is referred to when discussing school leadership (Gronn, 2003, as cited by Ng et al., 2015). Concepts like the leader-teacher relationship, collegiality, collaborative culture, learning organization, teacher leadership, and personal leadership all suggest that the power to decide that enhance teaching and learning in the learning environments must be given throughout the organization, even though the school head is still an essential component in organizational change (Ng, 2019). In the case of the four universities, it can be gleaned that the deans and coordinators have assimilated the school leadership function, and throughout the time, instructional leadership was fathomed by the teachers and staff of the college of nursing. The nursing organization became accustomed to the culture, and the teachers became leaders in the classroom or clinical setting, putting into practice the instructional leadership dimension of the system as well as nurturing the hearts and minds of the nursing students with the university's culture. The nursing leaders make the university culture in the realm of nursing education real.

According to Mahoney (2001), leaders are frequently characterized as visionaries who possess methods, a plan, and a desire to guide their teams and services toward a future objective. Successful leaders should be enthusiastic, dynamic, focused on finding solutions, motivating others, and seeking to inspire others. According to Bondas (2006), leaders that serve as motivators are respected, looked up to, and serve as examples for aspiring nursing leaders. The deans and coordinators of the COE colleges of nursing are senior nurses in academia and have evidently applied these characteristics to their typical day-to-day work to win the respect and trust of the teachers and lead the development of students towards their nursing journey. By demonstrating an illuminating leadership style, the deans and coordinators are in a commanding position to influence the successful development of teachers, staff, and nursing students. The nursing leaders have shifted their leadership journey from career to calling, amid challenges and circumstances. They are keeping the candle burning by way of maintaining professional standards, enabling the growth of competent future nurse practitioners, and encapsulating these with caring as the core of nursing. The role of the role of the nursing leader is to translate the university culture into nursing educational leadership.

This study is anchored in the comprehensive model of instructional leadership developed by Hallinger and Murphy (2013). Nursing leaders emphasize instructional leadership that addresses the three main components of this construct—defining the school's mission, overseeing the curriculum, and fostering a supportive learning environment—in order to satisfy the standards of a center of excellence. Ten functions of instructional leadership are further subdivided into these dimensions. The first broad dimension, which defines the school's mission, includes the first two tasks: establishing the aims of the school and conveying those goals. Curriculum coordination, student progress tracking, and supervision and evaluation of instruction comprise the three leadership responsibilities that make up the second dimension (Masina, 2020). The third dimension consists of five leadership responsibilities: safeguarding instructional time, encouraging professional growth, keeping a high profile, offering incentives to instructors, and creating conducive learning environments. Among the instructional leadership models now in use, the model that was presented was considered to be most extensively tested (Leithwood & Jantzi, 1999; Leithwood et al., 1999; Leithwood et al., 2004).

School leaders are also seen to create the school's mission statement in light of external considerations, such as the school's internal environment and initiatives and regulations from the Ministry of Education (Ng Foo Seong & Ho, 2012; Ho et al., 2020). This procedure shows the requirement to match national policies with objectives that suit the school's context. COE universities in the Philippines are directed to respond to the Commission on Higher Education's call for institutional development and innovation (IDI) objectives. Additionally, according to Ng (2019), school heads' definition of vision has expanded to consider contextual factors like “overarching” initiatives like Teach Less, Learn More and bilingual policy, as well as “cornerstone” policies in teaching and learning like bilingual policy and broad-based, holistic education. Thus, defining the school's mission is a tenet under which the university operates. The mission in itself is a vision that is anchored in values. Through the years, these colleges of nursing have revolutionized to become centers of excellence because the college in itself has inculcated the vision, mission, and core values of the university. The culture becomes a part of their work, a way of life, and the leaders' become influencers of the school culture. The leaders eloquently discuss the fundamental mission, prioritize the achievement of the students, and express essential principles in all they say and do. In this manner, they personify the core values of the university.

Western research on instructional program management highlights the significance of school heads' instructional accountabilities in arranging and overseeing curriculum and instruction, as well as keeping an eye on students' progress to determine the quality of instruction (Hallinger, 2013, 2015). The majority of school leaders recognized the value of overseeing curriculum, instruction, and student growth, according to previous research. Similar to educational leaders globally, school administrators must ensure that curriculum implementation and instruction are in line with the intended learning outcomes. The same practice is made for the COEs in nursing in the Philippines, as the CHED curriculum has ascertained the task as an integral role of the nursing faculty in the teaching and learning of the nursing curriculum. Consequently, the coordinators and dean's roles evolved to focus on exemplifying these tasks, like the ability to innovate, adapt, learn, and create new values, and recounting teachers and students progress and achievements. It becomes more about leaders as teachers with high visibility—leaders who personify the core values of the university.

The five leadership tasks that make up the dimension of supporting a healthy school learning climate are: safeguarding instructional time; encouraging professional development; keeping a high profile; offering incentives to teachers; and creating learning environments. These tasks are significant strategies that are mandatory in order to be recognized as centers of excellence, and they underscore the faculty and student development plans of the COEs. Moreover, CHED Nursing CMOs are outcomes-based and encompass both faculty and staff development, instructional time, and providing a learning climate. With this in mind, promoting a positive school learning climate is an imperative for leaders to focus on symbiotic relationships between people and the organization. The bedrock of an effective positive school learning climate is the capacity of the leader to be a visible servant, catalyst, and coach. The leader fosters a caring environment rooted in the culture of the university; in this manner, the positive school learning climate is personified by the leader inculcating the core values of the university.

The comprehensive model of instructional leadership developed by Hallinger and Murphy (1986, 2013) was realized by the four COE Colleges of Nursing. While each COE College of Nursing is an exemplar of distinctive instructional leadership, all four universities “touched” every aspect of the three dimensions of instructional leadership. The university's whole instructional leadership strategies have been embedded institutionally through the years, and the programs, specifically in the College of Nursing, have established a deepened sense of the culture, vision, mission, management of curriculum, and promoting a positive learning environment.

All things considered, the most popular model of instructional leadership explains three aspects: establishing the mission of the school, overseeing the curriculum, and cultivating a supportive learning environment (Hallinger, 2010, 2015; Hallinger & Murphy, 1986); these are fundamental elements that encompass the culture of a center of excellence university. Having gained perspective and acculturation, these characteristics are ingrained in the educational system, forming part of the university's basic principles and values. The deans' and coordinators' instructional leadership took on a new dimension as they realized the need to uphold the university's commitment to quality, personified the institution's core values, and translated the university culture into nursing academic leadership. The deans and coordinators of the Centers of Excellence—Colleges of Nursing in the Philippines are now leaders who emphasize compassionate leadership as the cornerstone of their instructional leadership practices, thanks to this change in the dimensions of instructional leadership.

Discussion and Conclusion

With the theme Personifying the Core Values of the University, framing the school's aims and expressing the school's goals are the first two responsibilities that are included in the first broad dimension, which defines the school's mission. The role of the deans and clinical coordinators in creating and communicating the distinct school vision with an emphasis on improved student understanding of the nursing curriculum highlighted these two leadership techniques (Hoeun et al., 2020).

A number of studies emphasized the methods that local school administrators used to formulate and carry out their school visions. Other stakeholders in the school community will get the vision once it has been formulated (Wang et al., 2016). The intermediate management or the top management (the head of the school) may be in charge of this (Koh et al., 2011; Ng et al., 2015). Koh et al. (2011) state that HODs in schools can efficiently assist school leaders in explaining school and MOE initiatives and rules through formal or informal department meetings while also gathering teacher input that will be relayed back to school officials. According to a school head (Ng et al., 2015), one strategy she used was to discuss the specifics of the school vision with all staff, students, and parents. She also mentioned having extremely prominent school displays that represented the objectives. In order to ensure that the university's objective appears in the teaching and learning processes, it is the head's responsibility to collaborate with others to create a vision that is appropriately context-based and to ensure that other school stakeholders are mindful of it. These are also practiced by the deans and coordinators across all four COEs of colleges of nursing. Seemingly, defining the school missions becomes a linear process for the institutions' stability, and through the years, it unfolds from the deans' descriptions on defining the vision to more profound collective statements that they become drivers of the university vision. The instructional leadership dimension shifted to personifying the core values of the university.

Curriculum coordination, student progress monitoring, and supervision and evaluation of instruction comprised the three leadership responsibilities in the second dimension. Apparently, this dimension was evident among the four COE colleges of nursing. The school head's responsibilities for overseeing, observing, and assessing the curriculum- and instruction-based activities at the school can be handled by the clinical coordinator, who reports the results of these procedures to the dean. In the current paradigm, the responsibilities of school heads are viewed as essential leadership duties. However, because the process is already rooted in the educational system of the university and ingrained in the college of nursing, it can be gleaned from the descriptions of the deans that their instructional leadership role has shifted to personifying the core beliefs of the university. They become symbolic instructional leaders, exemplifying their role beyond supervisory functions.

The third component, creating a pleasant learning environment, consists of five leadership responsibilities: safeguarding instructional time, encouraging professional growth, keeping a high profile, offering instructors incentives, and creating conducive learning environments. This component emphasizes how important it is to establish and preserve an educational environment in schools that fosters effective teaching and learning strategies as well as the professional growth of educators. The leadership functions included in this dimension were assumed by the deans and clinical coordinators of COE Colleges of Nursing and were regarded as highly influential leadership practices. These dimensions were already practiced in the university system across all four COEs. Clearly, the deans and clinical coordinators have imbued and fostered a caring and productive learning environment. This instructional leadership dimension has shifted the role of the dean to personify the core values of the university.

The instructional leadership of Centers of Excellence—Colleges of Nursing was grounded in the three dimensions of instructional leadership developed by Hallinger and Murphy (1986, 2013). The ability to establish the organizational conditions required by the systems and procedures to specify the university's mission, oversee the academic program, and foster a supportive learning environment by personifying the university's core values relies on the deans and coordinators.

On exploring the leaders of Centers of Excellence—Colleges of Nursing in the Philippines, the deans and coordinators are not only conductors of the dimensions and processes of instructional leadership nor implementors of the responsibilities and characteristics of a center of excellence, but they have shifted to a new dimension of leadership function, namely, personifying instructional leadership.

References

- Abreha, B. H. (2014). *An investigation into the principal's instructional role: a case of four secondary schools in Southern Nations, Nationalities and People's Region, Ethiopia* (Doctoral dissertation, University of South Africa).
https://uir.unisa.ac.za/bitstream/handle/10500/19065/thesis_bekuretsion_hailesilassie_abreha.pdf?isAllowed=y&sequence=1
- Barber, M., & Mourshed, M. (2007, September 1). *How the world's best-performing school systems come out on top*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/education/our-insights/how-the-worlds-best-performing-school-systems-come-out-on-top>
- Batac, C. (2007). *University and industry relations: a case study analysis of two marine science research institutes in the Philippines* (Master's thesis, University of Oslo).
<https://www.duo.uio.no/bitstream/handle/10852/30951/Batac.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Bondas, T. (2006). Paths to nursing leadership. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 14(5), 332-339.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2934.2006.00620.x>
- Burch, P., Bingham, A. J., & Miglani, N. (2020). Combining institutional and distributed frameworks in studies of school leadership. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 95(4), 408-422.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0161956X.2020.1800176>
- Commission on Higher Education. (2009). *Manual of regulations for private higher education*.
<https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Manual-of-Regulations-for-Private-Higher-Education.pdf>
- Gronn, P. (2003). *The new work of educational leaders: Changing leadership practice in an era of school reform*. SAGE Publications.
- Hallinger, P. (2003). Leading educational change: Reflections on the practice of instructional and transformational leadership. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 33(3), 329-352.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764032000122005>
- Hallinger, P. (2005). Instructional leadership and the school principal: A passing fancy that refuses to fade away. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 4(3), 221-239.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15700760500244793>
- Hallinger, P. (2007, August). *Research on the practice of instructional and transformational leadership: Retrospect and prospect* [Paper presentation]. ACER Research Conference 'The Leadership Challenge: Improving learning in schools', Melbourne, Australia.
https://research.acer.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1004&context=research_conference_2007
- Hallinger, P. (2010). Developing instructional leadership. In B. Davies & M. Brundrett (Eds.), *Developing successful leadership* (pp. 61-76). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-9106-2_5
- Hallinger, P. (2013). A conceptual framework for systematic reviews of research in educational leadership and management. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 51(2), 126-149.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/09578231311304670>
- Hallinger, P. (2015). The evolution of instructional leadership. In P. Hallinger & W. C. Wang (Eds.), *Assessing instructional leadership with the principal instructional management rating scale* (pp. 1-23). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-15533-3_1

- Hallinger, P., Heck, R. H., & Murphy, J. (2014). Teacher evaluation and school improvement: An analysis of the evidence. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, 26, 5-28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-013-9179-5>
- Hallinger, P., & Murphy, J. F. (1986). The social context of effective schools. *American Journal of Education*, 94(3), 328-355. <https://doi.org/10.1086/443853>
- Hallinger, P., & Murphy, J. F. (2013). Running on empty? Finding the time and capacity to lead learning. *NASSP Bulletin*, 97(1), 5-21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192636512469288>
- Ho, J., Ong, M., & Tan, L. S. (2020). Leadership of professional learning communities in Singapore schools: The tight-loose balance. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(4), 635-650. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143219833698>
- Hoeun, C. B., Asavisanu, P., & Merritt, M. (2020). The development of an instructional leadership model for outcome-based education at private higher education institutions in Cambodia. *Scholar: Human Sciences*, 12(2), 408-427. <http://www.assumptionjournal.au.edu/index.php/Scholar/article/view/4224>
- Koh, H. H., Gurr, D., Drysdale, L., & Ang, L. L. (2011). How school leaders perceive the leadership role of middle leaders in Singapore primary schools? *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 12(4), 609-620. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-011-9161-1>
- Leithwood, K., & Jantzi, D. (1999). Transformational school leadership effects: A replication. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 10(4), 451-479. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1076/sesi.10.4.451.3495>
- Leithwood, K., Jantzi, D., & Steinbach, R. (1999). *Changing leadership for changing times*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Leithwood, K., Seashore, K. S., Anderson, S., & Wahlstrom, K. (2004). *Review of research: How leadership influences student learning*. University of Minnesota, Center for Applied Research and Educational Improvement. <https://conservancy.umn.edu/bitstream/handle/11299/2035/CAREI%20ReviewofResearch%20How%20Leadership%20Influences.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Licuanan, P. B. (2012). *Policy-standard to enhance quality assurance (QA) in Philippine higher education through an outcomes-based and typology-based QA*. Commission on Higher Education. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CMO-No.46-s2012.pdf>
- Licuanan, P. B. (2017). *Policies, standards and guidelines (PSGs) for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program*. Commission on Higher Education. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CMO-15-s-2017.pdf>
- Liu, S., Xu, X., & Stronge, J. (2018). The influences of teachers' perceptions of using student achievement data in evaluation and their self-efficacy on job satisfaction: evidence from China. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 19, 493-509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-018-9552-7>
- Mahoney, J. (2001). Leadership skills for the 21st century. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 9(5), 269-271. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2834.2001.00230.x>
- Masina, S. K. (2020). *Exploring principals' instructional leadership practices in challenging contexts located in Johannesburg Central District: Case studies* (Master's thesis, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg). <https://wiredspace.wits.ac.za/server/api/core/bitstreams/84d0fc9a-e0f2-44c3-8c10-3afe9deb179e/content>
- Ng, F. S. D. (2019). Instructional leadership. In B. Wong, S. Hairon, & P. T. Ng (Eds.), *School leadership and educational change in Singapore* (pp. 7-30). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-74746-0_2
- Ng, F. S. D., Nguyen, T. D., Wong, K. S. B., & Choy, K. W. W. (2015). Instructional leadership practices in Singapore. *School Leadership & Management*, 35(4), 388-407. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2015.1010501>
- Ng Foo Seong, D., & Ho, J. M. (2012). How leadership for an ICT reform is distributed within a school. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 26(6), 529-549. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513541211251370>

- Pacis, M., Fontanilla, D. M., Panopio, A. R., & Concepcion, L. (2020). Correlation analysis of selected academic parameters and the Nurse Licensure Examination performance of the National University-Manila BSN graduates. *Journal of Sciences, Technology and Arts Research*, 6, 15-28. https://national-u.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/4.-JSTAR6_2-Panopio.pdf
- Puno, C. S. (2006). *Revised policies and standards on the center of excellence project*. Commission on Higher Education. <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CMO-No.55-s2006-1.pdf>
- Sana, E. A. (2010). Teaching and learning in health sciences education. In E. A. Sana (Ed.), *Teaching and learning in the health sciences* (pp. 3-10). UP Press.
- Stronge, J. H., Ward, T. J., & Grant, L. W. (2011). What makes good teachers good? A cross-case analysis of the connection between teacher effectiveness and student achievement. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 62(4), 339-355. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487111404241>
- Wang, L. H., Gurr, D., & Drysdale, L. (2016). Successful school leadership: case studies of four Singapore primary schools. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 54(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-03-2015-0022>
- Yin, R. K. (2015). *Qualitative research from start to finish*. Guilford Publications.